

Regional distribution of Binary numbers

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December 12, 2025

Abstract

Binary numbers, composed of only ones and zeros, form the foundation of modern computing systems. Their simplicity and efficiency make them essential for representing data, performing arithmetic operations, and implementing logic gates. The patterns in binary numbers have long fascinated computer scientists, particularly in relation to logic circuits, and mathematicians, especially due to their connection with combinatorial structures like Pascal's triangle. In this paper, we explore the distribution of binary numbers within the range $2^{b'-1}$ to $2^{b'-1}$ ($b' \in \mathbb{N}$). From this distribution, we derive explicit formulations for the total number of ones (hamming weight over a region) and zeros in binary representations. Additionally, we establish recurrence relations to describe these patterns, providing a deeper mathematical insight. Finally, we discuss efficient computational methods to determine the total number of ones and zeros in binary representations up to $2^{b'} - 1$, which has potential applications in digital signal processing, data compression, fast processing algorithms and computer science.

Keywords-Binary numbers, Principles of generating binary numbers, Nested interval, Hamming weight.

Mathematics Subject Classification: 11A63, 68R05.

1 Introduction

The binary numbers have been a great deal to computer scientists as it is the fundamentals of logic gates that lead to any parts in computers. The binary number system [1] is a number system that represents numbers using only two symbols: 0 and 1. It forms the foundation of modern computing and digital logic, playing a crucial role in the design and operation of logic gates, which underpin all computer hardware. The base of any digital computer system are logic gates [2] or circuits which performs logical operations on chunks of information represented digitally. The conceptual basis of the binary system can be traced back to Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz, who studied its structure in relation to the Chinese I Ching [3]. Due to his pioneering work, Leibniz is often regarded as the world's first computer scientist.

In this work, we analyze the distribution of ones and zeros in the binary representation of numbers within a specified region. Specifically on the basis of a total number of bits required to express in binary. The algorithm that generates binary numbers for a given number of bits has been well-documented in the literature [4], along with other related algorithms that explore applications of binary numbers in set theory, databases, and the Tower of Hanoi problem. Also, the logarithm can be obtained approximately from the binary number itself by simple counting [5], and the reduction of the resulting approximation error by a factor of six can be done. The count of ones in a binary sequence is known as the Hamming weight [6], a metric widely used in error detection and correction. Several modern processors incorporate specialized instructions, such as the POPCNT instruction on x86 architectures, to efficiently compute the Hamming weight.

In this paper, we present a method for determining the distribution of binary digits by calculating the total number of ones and zeros within a given range of binary numbers. Specifically, we focus on the region of numbers from $2^{b'-1}$ to $2^{b'} - 1$ where b' is the number of bits required to represent a number in binary form. The tight bounds for the total number of ones in the binary representation of numbers have been previously established in [7]. Building on this, we explore the regional distribution of ones by calculating the total number of ones in the range between $2^{b'} - 1$ and $2^{b'-1}$, which allows us to derive the total number of ones and zeros up to $2^{b'} - 1$. Our approach is based on the fundamental principle of binary number generation, which governs how binary numbers are successively formed. The total number of zeros in binary expansions has been addressed in [8]. While existing programs can compute the total number of ones and zeros less than or equal to the number of bits required to specify the number in the binary representation of numbers up to $2^{b'} - 1$, our method offers a more efficient and systematic approach to calculating these values.

1.1 Motivation

The Hamming weight of a binary number refers to the total number of ones in its binary representation, also known as the population count. The analysis of binary representations of natural numbers has provided key insights into determining the total Hamming weight within a specific range. Furthermore, the total length of the considered range correlates with the number of zeros, which is less than or equal to the total number of bits required to represent the numbers in binary.

1.2 Contribution

The classification of binary numbers based on the total number of bits required for their representation has partitioned the set of natural numbers into distinct regions. This division has proven useful in calculating the Hamming weight of binary numbers within each region. Furthermore, several recurrence relations have contributed to a deeper understanding of this partitioning. The total number of zeros and ones (i.e., the Hamming weight) within a given region and up to a specific number can be determined efficiently faster than any known algorithm in existing literature.

2 Literature survey

Binary numbers have been widely used in modern computers due to their simplicity and efficiency in digital systems. For an extensive overview of binary systems, see Bruck's seminal work [9]. This [10] paper explores the significance of binary numbers sequences of zeros and ones in computer science and their relevance in computational studies. A novel algorithm has been developed based on the interactions of RNA chains, which exhibit self-organizing capabilities. This [11] new algorithm, derived from the interactions of chains of RNA, specifically considers sequences of binary numbers (strings) and their interactions, providing insights into computational models inspired by biological systems. Additionally, a true binary system for representing real numbers, with both radix and cardinality of 2, has been introduced based on the Yin-Yang principle [12]. This system offers an alternative approach to numerical representation that aligns with fundamental mathematical principles. This binary system can not only represent all real numbers without using a sign, but also perform arithmetic and Boolean operations [13]. This [3] paper explores Gottfried Leibniz's formalization of the binary number system and its connection to Boolean logic, highlighting its significance in the evolution of computing machines. Leibniz's work [14] on the foundations of computing, the binary number system, and the step reckoner calculating machine was effective in computers. In order to evaluate the polynomials and to produce accurate mathematical tables, Babbage provided the design of the analytic engine [15](for its sketch and difference engine [16]), which provided the vision of a modern computer. Furthermore, the use of complex base binary numbers has been explored to represent complex

numbers as single units [17], there exists a need, at least for some problems, to treat a complex number as one unit [18]. Thus allowing for faster calculations [19]. This approach aims to simplify operations involving complex numbers in modern microprocessors, potentially enhancing computational efficiency. All numerical representations should be applicable to both positive and negative values. Furthermore, the representation techniques employed [20] should aim to maximize the accuracy of real number representation.

2.1 Disadvantages of existing methods

Although there are algorithms and formulas available to compute the Hamming weight of an individual number, obtaining the total Hamming weight within a specific region or up to a certain number requires calculating the Hamming weight for each number in that range and summing the results. This process is time-consuming and computationally intensive.

3 Objectives

3.1 Research Methodology

In this study, we explore various approaches to segmenting binary numbers and propose a systematic division based on the total number of bits required to represent a given binary number. Specifically, we define sections according to $b' \in \mathbb{N}$ where b' denotes the number of bits necessary for binary representation. Consequently, the entire binary system for natural numbers is structured into sections bounded by $2^{b'-1}$ to $2^{b'} - 1$. This segmentation reveals underlying patterns that facilitate efficient computation of the total number of ones and zeros within a given range. Notably, our approach enables faster calculations of these quantities for numbers up to $2^{b'} - 1$ compared to existing algorithms in the literature.

To achieve this, we begin by establishing key definitions, followed by the development of recurrence relations that capture the observed patterns. These relations are then used to formulate efficient computational methods. The derived results significantly enhance the efficiency of counting zeros and ones over a given region, demonstrating superior performance over conventional algorithms.

3.2 Key findings

The division of binary numbers into regions has been beneficial in determining the Hamming weight over a specific region and, hence up to a certain number. By calculating the total length of the interval, we deduced a method to precisely determine the number of zeros less than or equal to the total number of bits required to represent the number in binary.

3.3 Limitations

Although the total Hamming weight over a specific region of the form $2^{b'-1}$ to $2^{b'} - 1$ can be determined, this paper does not provide a formulation for finding the Hamming weight of an individual number. The Hamming weights up to a number can only be obtained when the number is of the form $2^{b'} - 1$.

4 preliminaries

4.1 The binary machine

The marble adding machine, a mechanical device that uses marbles to perform binary addition, was created by Matthias Wandel, a Canadian woodworker and engineer. A fascinating mechanical contraption that visually demonstrates the principles of binary counting using marbles and wooden levers.

Figure 1: Marble adding machine

This machine uses a cascading series of tilting levers to count in binary, similar to how a computer stores numbers using bits. He designed it as a playful and educational tool to demonstrate binary addition using a series of tracks, switches, and marbles to represent bits. The machine became popular for its clever design and unique approach to illustrating binary operations.

The machine has a series of flip-flop levers, each representing a binary bit. A marble acts as a 1, and an empty space represents a 0. As a new marble is dropped into the system, it toggles the first flip-flop lever. When a bit flips from 1 back to 0, it sends a marble to the next lever, just like a carry operation in binary addition. With each additional marble, the machine progresses through binary numbers (000, 001, 010, etc.), making it a physical representation of a binary counter.

4.2 Principle of generation of binary numbers

The principle of the generation of binary numbers can be analyzed by certain mathematical machines that generate the binary numbers. We will use certain definitions and terminologies to understand the principle of the generation of binary numbers.

Terminologies:

b' be the number of bits required to express the number in binary.

Definitions:

1. *Running machine*: The one bit machine which runs giving output 0_2 and 1_2 at a particular specified bit. It can also be called a one-bit requirement.

2. *Fixed machine*: The machine that is going to output fixed value (1_2) at a particular specified bit is called as Fixed machine.

3. *R-bit requirement*: It is the combination of R number of one bit requirement machines which iteratively produced by techniques of previous machines.

4. *Self-Step machine(SS)*: The machine which increments the output at its bit (first bit) when all the previous place value bits get terminated, starting off from 1 and it restarts all previous place value bits to start off from the beginning. After some time when all the previous place value bits get terminated again, the value increments again at its bit and restarts all the previous place value bits to start off from the beginning. The process continues until it reaches $(m-1)_{10}$.

4.2.1 Generating binary numbers by SS and running machine

The principle of generating binary numbers can be analyzed by using SS and a running machine where n bits are taken to generate the binary numbers from 2^{n-1} to $2^n - 1$. This method also uses the fixed machine for generating binary numbers which is also an SS machine that has only one so, its a static one (fixed) machine.

Let us construct a mathematical iterative machine to generate the binary numbers with the help of some observations, we will take one bit requirement as one bit machine which is going to be one bit slot machine producing 0 and 1, and two bit requirement as two bit machine which is going to be two bit slot machine and so on. This method often requires the previous n-1 bit requirement that uses other respective lower bit requirement machines and hence it's an iterative machine.

Let's take b' as the number of bits required to specify a number in binary. If $b' = 1$, two numbers are possible to express into binary which are 0 and 1, and if $b' = 2$, then there exist 2 and 3, and for $b' = 3$ then there exists 4,5,6,7 similarly, and so on.

At first one bit requirement machine gets started which produces 0 and 1 Now two bit requirement starts in this, we will keep the first bit as 1 fixed and

we add and run the one bit requirement in the last slot which is the second slot the process terminates with 11 which is 3 producing 10 and 11. Now the three bit requirement starts $b' = 3$ in this, we will keep 1 at first bit fixed this starts off by zeros at other bits and then we add and run with one bit requirement machine in the last slot which generates numbers which are 100 and 101 and now we remove the one bit requirement machine placed at last bit and add two bit requirement which produced 10 and 11 with the help of one bit requirement previously, to last two bits keeping 1 fixed, which produces 110 and 111 now the process has ended and then the process continues.

In general, for to generate the binary numbers in the region 2^{n-1} and $2^n - 1$ for $b' = n$ we start of by keeping first bit as one fixed in the entire process which is the fixed machine, this starts off by zeros at other bits and then we add and run with one bit requirement machine in the last slot which generate numbers which are 10...00 and 10...01 and after this terminated now we remove the one bit requirement machine placed at last bit and add two bit requirement machine which produced 10 and 11 with the help of one bit requirement to last two bits keeping 1 fixed, which produces 10...010 and 10...011 and after this terminated now we remove the two bit requirement machine placed at last two bit and add three bit requirement machine to last three bits which has 100,101,110 and 111 produced with the help of one and two bit requirement previously, keeping 1 fixed, which produces 10...0100, 10...0101, 10...0110 and 10...0111 and after this terminated we remove the three bit requirement machine placed at last three bit and add four bit requirement machine and the process continues. Continuing this kind of iteration machine procedure until all the bits get filled up as 111...(n-bits)1, terminating the process we complete the generation of binary numbers in the chosen region.

If we do from $b' = 1$ to n we get every binary representation for all the numbers from 1 to n . This is the principle of generating binary numbers by mathematical iteration machines.

5 Regional Representation of Binary numbers

Throughout the paper, we are going to use some notations, representations and definitions.

Notations: Let

$b' = n$ be the total number of bits required to specify a number in binary and n is used as a generalized variable.

$T_0(k)$ and $T_1(k)$ be the total number of zeros and ones in the binary representation of k respectively.

$\sum_{i=2^{b'}-1}^{2^{b'}-1} T_0(i)$ is the total number of zeros in the binary expansion of numbers in between the region from $2^{b'-1}$ to $2^{b'}-1$ less then or equal to total number of bits required to express the numbers in binary.

$\sum_{i=1}^{2^{b'}-1} T_0(i)$ is the total number of zeros in the binary expansion of numbers up to $2^{b'}-1$ less then or equal to total number of bits required to express the numbers in binary.

$\sum_{i=2^{b'}-1}^{2^{b'}-1} T_1(i)$ is the total number of ones in the binary expansion of numbers in between the region from $2^{b'-1}$ to $2^{b'}-1$.

$\sum_{i=1}^{2^{b'}-1} T_1(i)$ is the total number of ones in the binary expansion of numbers up to $2^{b'}-1$.

Representations: We are going to assign the place values to these binary representations of numbers in the following format.

place values: ...5	4	3	2	1	Decimal number
Binary representation: ...0	0	0	1	1	3

We need certain definitions and terminologies for the analysis of the observations, which serves as the regional distribution of binary numbers.

Regional binary sequences:

The binary sequences which counts the total number of ones which is used in describing the regional distribution of binary numbers is known as regional binary sequences .

There are two types of regional Binary sequences:

1. Binary-bit sequence.
2. Total binary bit sequence.

Nested end pairs:

Before going to the definitions of types of binary bit sequences we will go through the end pairs of nested interval sequences which we will use it to define the sequences.

The nested end pairs are the numbers that give each nested intervals end points in a defined nested interval sequence.

Example: consider Table-1 and defining the nested interval sequence as

$$\langle N_n \rangle = [2^{n-1}, 2^n - 1]; \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$$

-1

$$\Rightarrow N_1 = [1, 0]; N_2 = [2, 3]; N_3 = [4, 7]$$

and so on...

This is the sequences of nested sequences(N_i). Breaking down gives:

The end pairs of nested sequence $N_1 = [(0, 1)]$

The end pairs of nested sequence $N_2 = [(2, 3)]$
The end pairs of nested sequence $N_3 = [(4, 7), (5, 6)]$
and so on...

The above example provided will be used to define Binary-bit sequence.

1.Binary-bit sequence($\langle B_n \rangle$): The sequence obtained by the sum of ones present in the binary expansion of end pairs of each pair of N_i which is going to be a constant for each $i \in \mathbb{N}$ is known as Binary-bit sequence.

i.e,

$$N_1 = T_1(0) + T_1(1) = 0 + 1 = 1$$

$$N_2 = T_1(2) + T_1(3) = 1 + 2 = 3$$

$$N_3 = T_1(4) + T_1(7) = 1 + 3 = 4$$

$$N_3 = T_1(5) + T_1(6) = 2 + 2 = 4$$

and so on...

Therefore,

$$\langle B_n \rangle = 1, 3, 4, 5...$$

also

$$\langle B_1 \rangle = 1$$

$$\langle B_n \rangle = n + 1; \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$$

-1

2.Total binary bit sequence($\langle B_{rn} \rangle$): The total number of ones in between the region from 2^{n-1} to $2^n - 1$; $\forall n \in \mathbb{N} - \{1\}$, for $n=1; B_{r1} = 1$

In other words, the sequence which tells how many times N_i has repeated the sum of ones in end pairs in each of its sequences.

i.e, N_1 has 1 time repeated constant 1.

N_2 has 1 time repeated constant 3.

N_3 has 2 times repeated constant 4.

N_4 has 4 times repeated constant 5.

and so on...

$$\Rightarrow \langle B_{rn} \rangle = 1(1), 1(3), 2(4), 4(5)...$$

$$\Rightarrow \langle B_{rn} \rangle = 1(1), 2^0(3), 2^1(4), 2^2(5)...$$

$$\Rightarrow \langle B_{rn} \rangle = 1, 3, 8, 20...$$

In general,

$$\langle B_{r1} \rangle = 1$$

$$\langle B_{rn} \rangle = (n + 1)2^{n-2}; \forall n \in \mathbb{N} - \{1\}$$

which is the product of the total number of nested intervals formed for N_i and the constant obtained from the nested end pair which is binary-bit.

Note: 1. The total number of end pairs in the nested sequence is

$$\frac{(2^{b'} - 1) - (2^{b'-1}) + 1}{2}$$

which can be used to get the variable c in the equation-10

i.e., it varies from 0 to $\frac{(2^{b'} - 1) - (2^{b'-1}) + 1}{2} - 1$

$$\Rightarrow 0 \text{ to } 2^{b'-2} - 1$$

5.1 Observations

We partition the binary numbers into regions based on the number of bits required to express the number into binary is known as binary bit partition(table-1).

consider the table-1, the list of binary numbers partitioned into regions of the form $2^{b'-1}$ to $2^{b'} - 1$.

Decimal Number	Binary Representation	Decimal Number	Binary Representation	Decimal Number	Binary Representation
0	...0 0	16	...0 10000	32	...0 100000
1	...0 1	17	...0 10001	33	...0 100001
2	...0 10	18	...0 10010	34	...0 100010
3	...0 11	19	...0 10011	35	...0 100011
4	...0 100	20	...0 10100	36	...0 100100
5	...0 101	21	...0 10101	37	...0 100101
6	...0 110	22	...0 10110	38	...0 100110
7	...0 111	23	...0 10111	39	...0 100111
8	...0 1000	24	...0 11000	40	...0 101000
9	...0 1001	25	...0 11001	41	...0 101001
10	...0 1010	26	...0 11010	42	...0 101010
11	...0 1011	27	...0 11011	43	...0 101011
12	...0 1100	28	...0 11100	44	...0 101100
13	...0 1101	29	...0 11101	45	...0 101101
14	...0 1110	30	...0 11110	46	...0 101110
15	...0 1111	31	...0 11111	47- -	...0 101111- -

Table 1: Binary bit partition

We divided the binary numbers as of the total number of bits required to specify the number in binary. Based on that, we observed that

1. The recurrence relation for the total number of ones between the region from 2^{n-1} to $2^n - 1$ is

$$a_n = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} a_i + 2^{n-1} \quad (1)$$

2. The recurrence relation for the total number of ones up to $2^n - 1$ is

$$a_n = a_{n-1} + 2^{n-1} \quad (2)$$

3.

$$\langle B_n \rangle = T_1(2^{b'-1} + c) + T_1((2^{b'} - 1) - c) = b' + 1 \quad (3)$$

where c can take the values from 0 to $2^{b'-2} - 1$; $\forall b' \in \mathbb{N} - 1$; for $b' = 1$; $T_1(0) + T_1(1) = 1$.

4. The total number of ones in between the region $2^{b'-1}$ to $2^{b'} - 1$ is

$$\langle B_{rn} \rangle = \sum_{i=2^{b'-1}}^{2^{b'}-1} T_1(i) = (n+1)2^{n-2} \quad (4)$$

where $\langle B_{r1} \rangle = 1$.

5. The total number of ones up to $2^{b'} - 1$ is

$$\sum_{i=1}^{2^{b'}-1} T_1(i) = b'2^{b'-1} \quad (5)$$

were $\forall b' \in \mathbb{N}$

6. The recurrence relation to for the total number of zeros less than or equal to the total number of bits required to express in binary in between the region from 2^{n-1} to $2^n - 1$ is

$$a_n = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} a_i + 2^{n-1} - 2 \quad (6)$$

7. The recurrence relation to for the total number of zeros less than or equal to the total number of bits required to express in binary up to $2^n - 1$ is

$$a_n = a_{n-1} + 2^{n-1} - 2 \quad (7)$$

8. The total number of zeros in the binary expansion of numbers in between the region from $2^{b'-1}$ to $2^{b'} - 1$ less than or equal to the total number of bits required to express the numbers in binary is

$$\sum_{i=2^{b'-1}}^{2^{b'}-1} T_0(i) = (b')2^{b'-1} - (b'+1)2^{b'-2} \quad (8)$$

were $\forall b' \in \mathbb{N}$ (were $T_0(1) = 1$).

9. The total number of zeros in the binary expansion of a number up to $2^{b'} - 1$ less than or equal to the total number of bits required to express the

numbers in binary is

$$\sum_{i=1}^{2^{b'}-1} T_0(i) = 2 + 2^{b'-1}(b' - 2) \quad (9)$$

where $\forall b' \in \mathbb{N}$.

5.1.1 Analysis of Regional binary sequences

In this section, we are going to discuss the results observed from partition of binary numbers in $2^{b'-1}$ to $2^{b'} - 1$. we discuss the formulations in theorems and corollary format.

The equation-1 is a recurrence relation for the total number of ones in the region we prove the result in the following theorem.

Theorem 5.1. *The recurrence relation for the total number of ones between the region from 2^{n-1} to $2^n - 1$ is*

$$a_n = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} a_i + 2^{n-1}$$

Proof. Consider the table-1, by the principle of generating binary numbers we can observe that except the n^{th} place value row in the region between 2^{n-1} to $2^n - 1$ all the previous rows are the exact copy of all the previous regions and remaining spaces are filled with zeros, now at the n^{th} place value the total number of ones are in powers of two in accordance with the way we divided the region.

$$\Rightarrow a_n = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} a_i + 2^{n-1}$$

□

The equation-2 is a recurrence relation for the total number of ones up to $2^n - 1$. we prove the result in the following corollary.

Corollary 5.1.1. *The recurrence relation for the total number of ones up to $2^n - 1$ is $a_n = a_{n-1} + 2^{n-1}$*

Proof. Consider the table-1, by the principle of generating binary numbers and by the theorem-5.1 we can observe that except the n^{th} place value row all the previous rows are the exact copy of all the previous (a_{n-1}) and remaining spaces are filled with zeros, now at the n^{th} place value the total number of ones are in powers of two in accordance with the way we divided the region.

$$\Rightarrow a_n = a_{n-1} + 2^{n-1}$$

□

The equations-3 and 4 is binary bit sequence and total binary bit sequence. We prove both the results in the following theorem.

Theorem 5.2. *The Binary-bit sequence and Total binary bit sequence are of the form*

$$\langle B_1 \rangle = 1$$

$$\langle B_n \rangle = n + 1; \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$$

and

$$\langle B_{r1} \rangle = 1$$

$$\langle B_{rn} \rangle = (n + 1)2^{n-2}; \forall n \in \mathbb{N} - \{1\}$$

Proof. To prove that there is going to be a constant number in the amount of number of ones in each nested end pair in the taken region.

From the principle of generation of binary numbers, the total number of ones in the beginning and ending numbers in a taken region is going to have the general form of $(1+(0+0+\dots(n-1)\text{times}+0))$ and $(1+1+\dots n - \text{times}+1)$ respectively.

$$\Rightarrow \langle B_n \rangle = (1 + 0 + 0 + \dots(n-1)\text{times} + 0) + (1 + 1 + \dots n - \text{times} + 1)$$

[First end pairs sum]

$$\Rightarrow \langle B_n \rangle = 1 + (1 + 1 + \dots n - \text{times} + 1)$$

$$\Rightarrow \langle B_n \rangle = 1 + n; \forall n \in \mathbb{N} - \{1\}$$

Now, from the principle of generating binary numbers, the total number of ones in the next end pairs is going to have the general form of

$$\Rightarrow \langle B_n \rangle = (1+(0+0+\dots(n-2)\text{times}+0)+1)+((1+1+\dots(n-1) - \text{times}+1)+0)$$

[second end pairs sum]

$$\Rightarrow \langle B_n \rangle = 2 + (1 + 1 + \dots(n-1) - \text{times} + 1)$$

$$\Rightarrow \langle B_n \rangle = 2 + n - 1 = 1 + n; \forall n \in \mathbb{N} - \{1\}$$

Now, again from the principle of generating binary numbers, the total number of ones in the next end pairs is going to have the general form of

$$\Rightarrow \langle B_n \rangle = (1+(0+0+\dots(n-3)\text{times}+0)+1+0)+((1+1+\dots(n-2) - \text{times}+1)+0+1)$$

[third end pairs sum]

$$\Rightarrow \langle B_n \rangle = 2 + (1 + 1 + \dots (n - 2) - \text{times} + 1) + 1$$

$$\Rightarrow \langle B_n \rangle = 2 + n - 2 + 1 = 1 + n; \forall n \in \mathbb{N} - \{1\}$$

similarly,

$$\Rightarrow \langle B_n \rangle = (1 + (0 + 0 + \dots (n - 3) \text{times} + 0) + 1 + 1) + ((1 + 1 + \dots (n - 2) - \text{times} + 1) + 0 + 0)$$

[fourth end pairs sum] and so on...

i.e., At each step 1 is incremented and decremented at first and last number in the region respectively. Hence,

$$\Rightarrow \langle B_n \rangle = 1 + n; \forall n \in \mathbb{N} - \{1\}$$

Now to prove that the number of ones in the region that we have taken is in the form of $(1 + n)2^{n-2}; \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$

Consider the Table-1,

Now from the table-1 at n^{th} place value in the given region, By the principle of generation of binary numbers the number of ones in the specified region will be of the form 2^{n-1} ,

and the remaining, from $(n - 1)^{\text{th}}$ place value to 0^{th} place value the number of ones in the given region for each place value is in the form $\frac{2^{n-1}}{2}$.

Therefore in general, the total number of ones in the given region will be

$$(2^{n-1}) + (n - 1) \frac{(2^{n-1})}{2}$$

$$\Rightarrow \langle B_{rn} \rangle = (1 + n)2^{n-2}; \forall n \geq 1$$

□

Note: 1. The binary bit sequence can be written as

$$\langle B_n \rangle = T_1(2^{b'-1} + c) + T_1((2^{b'} - 1) - c) = b' + 1 \quad (10)$$

where c can take the values from 0 to $2^{b'-2} - 1; \forall b' \in \mathbb{N} - 1$; for $b' = 1$; $T_1(0) + T_1(1) = 1$.

2. The total binary bit sequence can be expressed as binary bit sequence as:

$$\langle B_{rn} \rangle = \sum_{i=m^{n-1}}^{m^n-1} T_1(i) = 2^{n-2} \langle B_n \rangle; \forall n \in \mathbb{N} - \{1\}.$$

The equation-5 gives the total number of ones up to $2^{b'} - 1$ which we are going to discuss in the following corollary.

Corollary 5.2.1. *The total number of ones up to $2^{b'} - 1$ is*

$$\sum_{i=1}^{2^{b'}-1} T_1(i) = b'2^{b'-1}$$

$\forall b' \in \mathbb{N}$

Proof. From the total number of ones in the binary expansion of numbers in between the region from $2^{b'-1}$ to $2^{b'} - 1$ is

$$\sum_{i=2^{b'-1}}^{2^{b'}-1} T_1(i) = \sum_{i=1}^{2^{b'}-1} T_1(i) - \sum_{i=1}^{2^{b'-1}} T_1(i) = (b'+1)2^{b'-2}$$

were $\forall b' \in \mathbb{N}$ (take $2^{b'-1} = 0$ for $b' = 1$).

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^{2^{b'}-1} T_1(i) &= \sum_{i=1}^{b'} (i+1)2^{i-2} \\ \Rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^{2^{b'}-1} T_1(i) &= \frac{1}{4} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{b'} i2^i + \sum_{i=1}^{b'} 2^i \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{2 - (b'+1)2^{b'+1} + b'2^{b'+2}}{(1-2)^2} + \frac{2(2^{b'}-1)}{(2-1)} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{4} (2 - (b'+1)2^{b'+1} + b'2^{b'+2} + 2^{b'+1} - 2) \\ &= \frac{1}{4} (-b'2^{b'+1} + b'2^{b'+2}) \\ \sum_{i=1}^{2^{b'}-1} T_1(i) &= b'2^{b'-1} \end{aligned}$$

□

The equation-6 is the recurrence relation for the total number of zeros in the region from 2^{n-1} to $2^n - 1$. we will discuss in the following theorem.

Theorem 5.3. *The recurrence relation for the total number of zeros in between the region from 2^{n-1} to $2^n - 1$ less than or equal to total number of bits required to express a number in binary is*

$$a_n = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} a_i + 2^{n-1} - 2$$

Proof. Consider the table-1, by the principle of generating binary numbers we can observe that except the n^{th} place value row in the region between 2^{n-1} to $2^n - 1$ all the previous rows are the exact copy of all the previous regions and remaining spaces are filled with zeros which are in powers of two in accordance with the way we divided the region.

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow a_n &= \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} a_i + \sum_{i=1}^{n-2} 2^i \\ \Rightarrow a_n &= \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} a_i + \frac{2(2^{n-2} - 1)}{(2 - 1)} \\ \Rightarrow a_n &= \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} a_i + 2^{n-1} - 2 \end{aligned}$$

□

The equation-7 is the recurrence relation for total number of zeros up to $2^n - 1$ which we are going to discuss in the following corollary.

Corollary 5.3.1. *The recurrence relation for the total number of zeros up to $2^n - 1$ less than or equal total number of bits required to express a number in binary is*

$$a_n = a_{n-1} + 2^{n-1} - 2$$

Proof. Consider the table-1, by the principle of generating binary numbers and by the theorem-5.3 we can observe that except the n^{th} place value row all the previous rows are the exact copy of all the previous (a_{n-1}) and remaining spaces are filled with zeros which are in powers of two in accordance with the way we divided the region.

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow a_n &= a_{n-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{n-2} 2^i \\ \Rightarrow a_n &= a_{n-1} + \frac{2(2^{n-2} - 1)}{(2 - 1)} \\ \Rightarrow a_n &= a_{n-1} + 2^{n-1} - 2 \end{aligned}$$

□

The equation-8 gives the total number of zeros in the region $2^{b'-1}$ to $2^{b'} - 1$. we are going to discuss in the following theorem.

Theorem 5.4. *The total number of zeros in the binary expansion of numbers in between the region from $2^{b'-1}$ to $2^{b'} - 1$ less than or equal to the total number of bits required to express the numbers in binary is*

$$\sum_{i=2^{b'-1}}^{2^{b'}-1} T_0(i) = (b')2^{b'-1} - (b' + 1)2^{b'-2}$$

$$\forall b' \in \mathbb{N} \text{ were } T_0(1) = 1$$

Proof. From the total number of bits required to specify the numbers in binary form in the taken region is $(b')2^{b'-1}$.
and hence,

{The total number of zeros in the binary expansion of numbers in between the region from $2^{b'-1}$ to $2^{b'} - 1$ less than or equal to the total number of bits required to express the numbers in binary}={The total number of bits required to express the numbers in binary in between the region from $2^{b'-1}$ to $2^{b'} - 1$ }-
{The total number of ones in binary expansion of numbers in between the region from $2^{b'-1}$ to $2^{b'} - 1$ }

From the table-1

The total number of bits required to express the numbers in binary in between the region from $2^{b'-1}$ to $2^{b'} - 1$ = b' {Total number of numbers in the region from $2^{b'-1}$ to $2^{b'} - 1$ }

$$= \frac{b'(2^{b'-1}-2^{b'-1}+1)}{2} = \frac{b'2^{b'}}{2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2}\right) = b'\{2^{b'-1}\}$$

From the definition of total binary bit sequence and theorem-5.2
{The total number of ones in the binary expansion of numbers in between the region from $2^{b'-1}$ to $2^{b'} - 1$ }

$$= (b' + 1)2^{b'-2}; \forall b' \in \mathbb{N} - 1 \quad (11)$$

By the equations-5.1.1 and 11 we get,

$$\sum_{i=2^{b'-1}}^{2^{b'}-1} T_0(i) = \sum_{i=1}^{2^{b'}-1} T_0(i) - \sum_{i=1}^{2^{b'-1}} T_0(i) = (b')2^{b'-1} - (b' + 1)2^{b'-2}$$

□

The equation-9 gives the total number of zeros up to $2^{b'} - 1$. we are going to discuss in the following corollary.

Corollary 5.4.1. *The total number of zeros in the binary expansion of a number up to $2^{b'} - 1$ less than or equal to the total number of bits required to express the numbers in binary is*

$$\sum_{i=1}^{2^{b'}-1} T_0(i) = 2 + 2^{b'-1}(b' - 2)$$

where $\forall b' \in \mathbb{N}$

Proof. From the total number of zeros in the binary expansion of numbers in between the region from $2^{b'-1}$ to $2^{b'} - 1$ less than or equal to the total number of bits required to express the numbers in binary is

$$\sum_{i=2^{b'-1}}^{2^{b'}-1} T_0(i) = (b')2^{b'-1} - (b' + 1)2^{b'-2}$$

where $T_0(1) = 1$, Hence we add 1 while taking summation,

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^{b'} T_0(i) &= 1 + \sum_{i=1}^{b'} (i2^{i-1}) - (i+1)2^{i-2} \\ &= 1 + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{b'} i2^i - \frac{1}{4} \sum_{i=1}^{b'} (i2^i + 2^i) \\ &= 1 + \frac{1}{4} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{b'} i2^i - \sum_{i=1}^{b'} 2^i \right) \\ &= 1 + \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{2 - (b'+1)2^{b'+1} + b'2^{b'+2}}{(1-2)^2} - \frac{2(2^{b'} - 1)}{(2-1)} \right) \\ &= 1 + 1 + b'2^{b'-1} - 2^{b'} \\ &\Rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^{b'} T_0(i) = 2 + 2^{b'-1}(b' - 2) \end{aligned}$$

□

6 Results and Performance Evaluation

The principle of generation of binary numbers was established, leading to the categorization of binary representations of natural numbers into distinct regions, within which several observations were established. Certain results were analyzed using recurrence relations, which provided insight into the underlying patterns of binary distributions. The total number of ones and zeros, less than or equal to the number of bits required to express the numbers in binary within each region, were examined in detail. By utilizing this analysis, the cumulative count of ones and zeros up to a specific number was determined.

7 Conclusion and Enhancement

7.1 conclusion

The Hamming weight over a specific region was determined, hence establishing an upper limit. This corresponds to get the number of zeros that is less than or equal to the number of bits required to represent it in binary, and these findings were used to derive a systematic method for predicting the binary properties of natural numbers across different regions. The patterns of ones and zeros observed were crucial in understanding the distribution and frequency of binary digits in a given range. This allowed for a comprehensive regional distribution model for binary numbers, which could potentially be applied to various fields of number theory, computer science, and digital systems. Ultimately, the results highlight the importance of binary structure and offer new avenues for further investigation into the behavior of natural numbers in binary form.

7.2 Future Enhancement

The regional distribution for binary numbers has been established. This concept will now be extended to other base systems. The Hamming weight over a region has also been determined. We aim to further this by analyzing the Hamming weight at each place value within a region, up to a specific number corresponding to that place value. Extending such regional distributions to other bases will allow us to determine the total number of digits—zeros, ones, twos, and so on... in any positional numeral system. Subsequently, we will focus on computing the total sum and product of digits within a region and across individual place values, followed by a detailed study of their properties.

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